

Building an information-resilient society*

A two-day international conference was held recently to discuss the pivotal role of information ecosystem in connecting people, fostering understanding, and empowering individuals, thus contributing to building a more interconnected and harmonious society.

The conference featured six primary subthemes, each addressing crucial aspects of information resilience. Participants engaged in discussions ranging from building data-resilient communities to leveraging frontier technologies for societal well-being. Topics included data governance, crisis management, the role of information centres and the intersection of information resilience with the sustainable development goals (SDGs). There were five plenary sessions and ten technical sessions. Thirty-eight papers were presented from around the world, both in physical and virtual modes. The conference provided an excellent opportunity for researchers, academics and practitioners to exchange ideas and knowledge in the emerging area and develop effective strategies that enhance the capacity of information ecosystems to withstand and overcome future crises, while maximizing societal benefits even during non-crisis periods.

Sabuj Kumar Chaudhuri in his welcome address, emphasized the essence and significance of the conference in building an information-resilient society to mitigate vulnerabilities and combat future crises. He set the tunes, introduced the dynamics of the conference, and urged the participants to debate, brainstorm, and contribute to understanding the transdisciplinarity of this applied concept in order to connect the dots.

Animesh Kumar (United Nations Disaster Risk Reduction Office (UNDRR) in Bonn, Germany) delivered the keynote address on 'risk-informed development and climate action'. He highlighted role of UNDRR in minimizing disaster risk and

linking it with the SDGs. Kumar underscored the significance of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (2015–2030), outlining its four priorities for action and seven global targets. He emphasized the need for a proactive shift from reactive crisis management to sustainable risk management embedded within sustainable development, especially in light of escalating disaster risks exacerbated by climate change. Kumar also stressed the importance of a big data and information revolution, coupled with ethical and sustainable practices, to address emerging information needs for effective disaster risk management and climate action, resonating with the attendees, and emphasizing the critical integration of risk-informed development and climate resilience into global agendas.

Sayantan Mandal (IIT, Jammu) addressed the escalating issue of emerging tourist destinations in the Himalayan region, particularly Himachal Pradesh and Ladakh. He highlighted the absence of regulations in these areas compared to major tourist destinations, leading to unchecked pollution and urbanization. Mandal emphasized the urgent need for sustainable development practices to preserve the delicate socio-ecological balance of the region, which is under threat due to commercialization and the influence of social media travel vloggers. His lecture critically evaluated the prevailing development narrative and proposed viable measures for the sustainable growth of emerging tourist destinations in the Himalaya. Mandal also highlighted the detrimental impact of unregulated and thoughtless commercialization and urbanization in these areas, advocating for balanced and environmentally conscious strategies to ensure the long-term well-being of the region.

Souran Chatterjee (University of Plymouth, UK) spoke on the concept of achieving high well-being with low energy demand, exploring its feasibility amidst current challenges like the COVID-19 pandemic and energy crises. He emphasized the intricate interplay between energy, society, economy and the environment, stressing the importance of understanding energy systems to achieve climate neutrality. Chatterjee highlighted the significance of

empirical modelling to explore pathways for energy reduction and underscored the benefits of investing in demand-side measures, including improved health, productivity and economic growth. His research findings provided compelling evidence for the potential of demand-side measures to enhance energy resilience while achieving multiple socio-economic benefits.

Doronina Iryna (Technical University Munich, Germany) delivered a lecture on the impact of war on the energy sector, focusing on resilient recovery through wind and solar energy utilization. Her study meticulously mapped the energy infrastructure of Ukraine pre-war and assessed damages incurred during conflict. By identifying suitable areas for renewable energy, the study offers a pathway for low-carbon and conflict-resilient reconstruction. The lecture underscored the significance of renewable energy in achieving sustainable recovery objectives, aligning with European directives. Additionally, the comprehensive dataset obtained enables the utilization of advanced technologies like machine learning and artificial intelligence for forecasting and decision-making in energy planning.

Baskaran Angathevar (Universiti Malaya, Malaysia) delivered lecture on capacity building for the implementation and evaluation of policies advancing the SDGs, focusing on environmental sustainability practices among small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) in the Global South. He highlighted the urgent need for SMEs to embrace sustainability practices, especially in light of their significant economic contribution and potential environmental impact. The lecture addressed the critical gap in green practice adoption among SMEs and proposed innovative solutions to promote sustainable consumption and production. Angathevar's insights underscored the essential role of SMEs in achieving the SDGs and emphasized the importance of North–South capacity-building collaborations to effectively address this challenge.

Sascha Dov Bachmann (University of Canberra, Australia) delivered a lecture on the relevance of cognitive warfare, focusing on platforms like TikTok and their impact on Generation Z. He highlighted how state and non-state actors utilize psychological

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operations to influence public opinion, particularly evident in recent conflicts like the Hamas–Israel conflict. Bachmann emphasized the role of cognitive information warfare in targeting young audiences and undermining societal cohesion through disinformation. His presentation underscored the necessity of a comprehensive approach involving all stakeholders to effectively address this threat.

Olha Nimko (Virginia Tech, USA) spoke on refugee food security, delving into its intricate dynamics and drawing on interdisciplinary perspectives. She unravelled the multifaceted factors, policy implications and lessons learned from Ukraine's resilience during conflict. By analysing various influences such as individual, community, institutional, environmental and policy-related factors, the lecture explored access to nutritious food among displaced populations. It synthesized the existing literature and empirical evidence to shed light on determinants like education, employment, cultural practices and government policies. The lecture also highlighted the resilience of Ukrainian refugees amidst conflict, offering valuable insights

for addressing food insecurity in the context of refugees and informing policy and practice for targeted interventions.

Vira Ohorodnyk and Mariia Markina (Kyiv National Economic University, Ukraine) delivered a lecture on enhancing smart infrastructure for sustainable development and resilient regions, particularly focusing on wartime Ukraine. Their research delved into implementing smart infrastructure in cities, leveraging the latest technologies to contribute to the SDGs. Through a comparative analysis of e-governance implementation worldwide and using data envelopment analysis, they identified key factors influencing sustainable development. Their insights shed light on reforming state policies to promote smart infrastructure and digitalization, offering valuable guidance for policymakers and scientists to improve implementation efficiency and achieve the SDGs amidst challenging circumstances. Additionally, they discussed a pilot project named 'DREAM' (Digital Restoration Ecosystem for Accountable Management), which works on building community resilience in wartime Ukraine.

The conference was meticulously crafted to foster substantial exchanges and collaboration among attendees. Plenary sessions hosted stimulating discussions guided by esteemed scholars, while technical sessions offered avenues for comprehensive exploration of particular subtopics. The conference served as a forum for interdisciplinary discourse and cooperation in addressing the challenges posed by evolving information landscapes. Through insightful presentations, vibrant discussions and networking opportunities, the participants reaffirmed their commitment to building resilient information ecosystems that can withstand crises and contribute to sustainable societal well-being. As the conference drew to a close, the participants departed with renewed inspiration and a shared vision of an information-resilient society poised to navigate the complexities of the modern age.

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